

Mechanical Properties of Concrete Manufactured Using Amorphous Silica and Waste Ceramics: An Experimental Investigation

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Abstract:

Researchers are continuously studying the properties and functionality of cement and other aggregates, which are made from a combination of modern materials and different waste. In the current study, a series of experiments were conducted to compare the use of three different types of mixes. In the first mix, amorphous silica was used in place of cement; in the second, Waste Ceramics was used in place of sand; and in the third mix, both materials were combined to create concrete of M20 grade. These materials were used in place of cement and sand in varying amounts, such as 0%, 10%, 15%, 20% and 30%. The properties analyzed were workability by Slump cone and the compressive strengths after 3, 21, and 28

days. The main conclusions is the addition of amorphous silica affects consistency and setting time, as well as increasing compressive strength up to a certain limit. However, it has been observed that workability of concrete increases with the combined use of Amorphous Silica and Waste Ceramic Tiles. Compressive strength: It has been observed Maximum C3 compressive strength is found at 20% replacement of cement with Amorphous Silica after 3, 21 and 28 days of curing. Maximum compressive strength is found at 20% replacement of sand with Waste Ceramics after 3, 21 and 28 days of curing. Maximum XV compressive strength is found at 20% replacement of both cement and sand after 3, 21 and 28 days of curing. Compressive strength of concrete mix was increased slowly when both the chief ingredients were replaced by Amorphous Silica and Waste Ceramic Tiles. Split tensile strength at 3 days, 21 days and 28 days increased up to 20% and then decreases. Flexural strength at 3 days, 21 days and 28 days increased up to 20% and then decreases.

Keywords: *Amorphous Silica, Waste Ceramics, Wokability, Compressive Strength, Split tensile strength, flexural strength.*

Introduction

One of the most crucial building materials used in the construction sector is concrete. Urban development has led to an increase in the demand for concrete over time. As a result, there is a growing need for cement, which is a binder in concrete. Because cement production emits large amounts of carbon dioxide gas, it has an adverse effect on the environment. High temperatures are also necessary for the production of cement, as is the depletion of natural resources through raw material mining (limestone and clay quarry). As a result, scientists are always looking for new, environmentally friendly materials to replace OPC in concrete without compromising the material's strength or quality. When silicon metal or ferrosilicon alloys are produced, amorphous (non-crystalline) silicon dioxide (SiO₂) is a byproduct. As seen in this picture, electric furnaces are used to produce silicon metal and its alloys. Woodchips, coal, and quartz are the raw materials. Instead of being dumped into the ground, furnace smoke is gathered and sold as silica fume. This material's application as a mineral admixture in concrete is arguably its most significant one. Silica fume is not the same as fumed silica, which is amorphous silica made from silica using the flame method. Whereas silica fume has an average particle size of 0.1-0.15 μm, fumed silica has an average particle size of 7–40 nm. The individual particles have a size of about 1/100th that of an ordinary cement particle.

Additional calcium-silicate-hydrate (C-S-H) gel is created when nano silica is added to cement and reacts with the calcium hydroxide generated during the hydration process. This gel improves the material's overall strength and durability by plugging the tiny holes in the concrete matrix.

Currently, AF is widely used as a supplementary cementing material (SCM) to enhance the strength and durability of concrete. In many applications, concrete containing SF has produced greater compressive strengths, increased resistance to sulfates and acids, and decreased permeability to chlorides. As a result, AF-OPC in both new construction and

rehabilitation projects, concrete is widely used in a range of loading scenarios and unfavourable environments.

India produces 100 million tons of ceramics annually. India is among the top three nations in the world in terms of tile production. The output from 2011–12. The value of 267 in Int. J. Chem. Sci.: 14(S1), 2016 was roughly 600 million square meters. This massive output of ceramic tiles is the result of the housing industry's boom as well as government initiatives that have fueled the industry's rapid expansion. Within the ceramic industry, waste material amounts to 15% to 30% of total production. Even though it has been done, very little waste has been recycled in this manner from ceramic materials. Its application in other industries is therefore becoming increasingly necessary. The final user of all ceramic wastes, the construction sector, can help address this environmental issue. Utilization of Waste Ceramics or other desecrates materials such as Amorphous Silica in preparing concrete for various civil engineering projects is a subject of high significance. The addition of additional components to mortar or concrete changes a number of its properties, including relative performances, strength, and compaction factor.

Objectives of the Study

The chief reason of this present investigation is to observe the likelihood of waste industrial products such as Amorphous Silica and ceramic waste powder in concrete construction. The present work identifies about partial replacement of cement and sand by amorphous silica and waste ceramics. Following are the important objectives in the present investigation –

- To determine basic test in laboratory to find physical property and chemical of cement and sand.
- To determine workability of concrete by slump cone apparatus and compaction factor test.

- To investigate mechanical properties of concrete such as Compressive strength test, split tensile strength test and Flexural strength test.
- To determine the optimum replacement of chief ingredients, in terms of workability and mechanical properties of concrete with these materials.

Literature Review

Bijen (1996) calculate the Effect of fly ash and silica fume on compressive and fracture performances of concrete and concluded development of strength properties of concrete by mixing different proportion of fly ash and silica fume.

Nivetha (2002) This review article about the study of compressive strength in concrete by mixing waste construction materials such as brick dust and ceramic waste as a partial replacement of fine aggregate. This partial replacement of sand is done in different percentage of sand is replaced with of brick dust and of ceramic waste. The test result says that replacement of ceramic dust and brick dust gives the maximum compressive strength to the concrete. Accumulation of waste marble dust in cement has been presented by Barbhuiya (2009) in this work cement mortar and concrete composed by applying marble dust have been found to be improved, with the addition of marble dust. Concrete composed adding of marble dust as replacement of sand reveals improved act compared to replacement of cement. The chief idea of this investigation has been found to be examine the opportunity of utilizing waste marble dust in cement and concrete making.

A study has been conducted by Gonen and Yazicioglu (2009) for inspecting the influence of binary and ternary blend of mineral admixtures on the short and long term performances of concrete and ultimately made a conclusion that concrete properties are improved in fresh and hardened states.

Aruntaş in 2010 examined the blended cements produced by using the building stone powder

were out to sulfate concentration for unusual properties. Prepared mortar specimens had been cured under water for 28 days and then exposed to several different extents of sodium sulfate solution for large number of days. Performances of cements had been determined by testing properties like compressive and tests. In mixed binders exclusively cements produced by substituting waste provides like strength data when compared with ordinary Portland cement at the ages of different curing days.

The usefulness of waste marble dust as preservative material combine together with cement is examined by Aliabdo et al. (2014). In order to obtain waste marble dirt added cements for this plan, marble dust and Portland cement ashes were mixed together at varying percentages by weight and combine ratios. Using the obtained cements, mortar prisms of standard cube size were created artificially. Strength tests on various days of curing have been accepted for these mortar prisms.

Emre Sancak and Şükrü Özkan (2015) studied the presentation of glass powder in concrete in the real situations, a field examination has been performed by means of a 40 MPa concrete combination, including and considering a range of proportions of glass powder in and as cement replacement. A number of mixtures were created, the majority of which also contained sand-sized particles of screened glass, and these mixtures were utilized to cast multiple concrete slabs. The compressive and separating tensile strength, shrink and rise, ultrasonic pulse velocity, and chloride permeability of concrete cast have all been tested. Basic models had been cut for the same purpose as well as micros assessment from slabs of varying life spans. Comparing mixtures with glass powder blend, the alkali reactivity and drying shrinkage showed acceptable results. The outcomes revealed that GLP can be incorporated into high strength concrete at considerable proportions such as 20 – 30% to substitute of cement. Application of glass powder provides for substantial well utilization of waste glass in prepared mixes and noteworthy changes in the production of harmful gases to environment.

Sivaprakash et al. (2016) Finding appropriate substitutes that can replace sand entirely or in large quantities is urgently needed due to the rising demand for river sand and the declining supply of it. Numerous studies examine the impact of various waste products, including crushed rock flour, foundry bed waste, glass sheet powder, incinerated sewage sludge, and building demolition waste, in partially replacing river sand. One of the ongoing study areas that examines the efficacy of replacement in all facets of building materials is the use of ceramic waste. Using ceramic waste to create environmentally friendly concrete is crucial. This work examines the mechanical strength qualities of M25 grade concrete using an experimental investigation that uses ceramic waste to partially replace sand in the concrete. The samples were cured for several lengths of time, ranging from 7 days to 28 days, and were cast with 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, and 50% replacement of sand utilizing ceramic waste in order to investigate mechanical parameters including compressive, split tensile, and flexural strength. In light of the needs for the mechanical qualities of concrete, the ideal proportion addition of ceramic waste is examined.

El-Nadoury (2022) Producing sustainable concrete at the lowest practical cost is the industry's current problem. The need for an excessive quantity of cement is one barrier to that. Cement may be substituted in part with by-product materials that have the right pozzolanic index to reduce the amount of cement. During the manufacture of rice and tiles, two by-products are notably formed: rice husk ash (RHA) and ceramic waste powder (CWP). By partially replacing cement with these by-products, landfill space, concrete costs, and the greenhouse gas emissions caused by cement manufacture are all decreased. This study examines the impact of substituting CWP for cement in amounts of 5%, 15%, 20%, 25%, and 30%. Different amounts of RHA—5%, 10%, 15%, and 25%—were added to the mixture along with the ideal CWP. The proportions of the concrete mixture produced M35-grade concrete. Workability, compressive, splitting tensile, and flexural strengths of the concrete were evaluated. The outcomes are contrasted

with traditional concrete that has no replacement. The best proportion for replacing cement with CWP is 20%, according to the results. It results in increases of 11%, 20%, and 12.5% in the compressive, splitting tensile, and flexural strengths, respectively. Tensile and flexural strength are unaffected by an increase in percentage up to 30%, however compressive strength is severely impacted. Adding CWP and RHA to cement blend further enhances its mechanical qualities. In comparison to the control concrete, the 20% CWP/10% RHA combination offers higher strength; it boosts the compressive, tensile, and flexural strengths by 14%, 28%, and 19%, respectively.

Sivakumar (2022) This study examined the use of waste ceramic as a substitute for fine and coarse aggregates. For the current study, specimens containing fine and coarse aggregates at different percentage levels were prepared using ceramic waste. The compressive strength, split tensile strength, and flexural strength of concrete were greater than those of the other mixtures when an optimal amount of ceramic waste was used.

Zerihunet al. (2022) This review paper's primary objective was to investigate the physical and chemical characteristics of agricultural crop wastes and their potential as a partial replacement in the manufacturing of concrete and mortar. The following ashes were chosen for review: groundnut ashes (GNA), rice husk ashes (RHA), corncob ashes (CCA), banana ashes (BNLA), bamboo ashes (BLA), and sugarcane bagasse ashes (SCBA). These agricultural wastes' chemical makeup indicated that they are mostly made up of alumino-siliceous compounds that meet the criteria for pozzolanic materials. They have more surface area and finer particle size than cement. Concrete's mechanical properties (compressive and tensile strength), microstructure (scanning electron microscopy, derivative thermogravimetry, and X-ray diffraction), durability (ultrapulse velocity, water absorption, and sulphate attack), and fresh concrete properties (consistency, workability, and setting time) were all impacted by partially substituting cement with BLA, BNLA, CCA, GNA, RHA, and SCBA. When used in partial

substitution of cement, BLA, CCA, RHA, and SCBA reduced the workability of the concrete due to their smaller particle sizes. The partial replacement of cement in concrete with BLA, RHA, and SCBA led to enhanced mechanical performance because densified tetrahedral gel was created through a subsequent reaction involving amorphous silica. As a result, consistent and denser morphology developed, and durability improved as hydrated gel's densification rose. Overall, the analysis showed that crop wastes from agriculture meet the requirements for pozzolanic materials and have a great potential to substitute cement by up to 10% without affecting the quality of the concrete.

Naresh (2023) Concrete is enhanced by the addition of nano silica to improve its tensile and compressive strengths. The strength of concrete is enhanced when nano silica particles are added because they react with calcium hydroxide to form more calcium silicate hydrate. This may lead to concrete that has a longer service life and better resistance to corrosion and cracking. The goal of the experiment was to replace 0%, 0.5%, 1.0%, 1.5%, 2.0%, and 2.5% of the cement in M30 grade concrete with nano silica. The results of the test indicate that on the seventh, fourteenth, and twenty-eighth days after curing, the concrete's early-age compressive strength

and split tensile strength had significantly increased. The project's ultimate result will generally be advantageous for the use of nano-silica concrete in civil engineering construction projects.

Experimental Data

Table 1. Physical Properties of Cement

S. No.	Properties	Results of Conducted Tests
1	Fineness	8%
2	Specific Gravity	3.15
3	Normal Consistency	33%
4	Initial Setting Time	50 min
5	Final Setting Time	400 min

Table 2. Setting Time Test Results

Properties	Replacement (%)	Setting Time (minutes)
Initial Setting Time	0	31
	10	40
	20	42
	30	45
Final Setting Time	0	601
	10	618
	20	623
	30	630

Table 3 Ratio of Weight of Each Constituent (Kg) in Concrete for Preparing Mixes Weight of Materials (Kg)

Mix design	Replacement %	Cement (Kg)	Amorphous Silica	CA(Kg)	Sand (FAin Kg)	W/C	Waste Ceramic Tiles (Kg)
M20	0	400	0	1136.55	726.64	0.5	0
	10	360	40	1136.55	653.64	0.5	40
	15	340	60	1136.55	617.64	0.5	60
	20	320	80	1136.55	580.64	0.5	80
	30	280	120	1136.55	507.64	0.5	120

Table 4. Mix Proportion

Water	Cement	Sand	Coarse aggregate
0.5	1	1.9	3.1

Table 5. Proportion of Ingredients for M1 Mixes after Replacing Cement by Amorphous Silica

Weight of Materials (Kg)				
% Replacement	Cement	Amorphous Silica	Aggregate	Sand
0	400	0	1136.55	726.64
10	360	40	1136.55	726.64
15	340	60	1136.55	726.64
20	320	80	1136.55	726.64
30	280	120	1136.55	726.64

Table 6. Proportion of Ingredients for M2 Mixes by Replacing Sand by Waste Ceramic Tiles

Weight of Materials (Kg)				
% Replacement	Cement	Sand	Aggregate	Waste Ceramic Tiles
0	400	726.64	1136.55	0
10	400	653.64	1136.55	40
15	400	617.64	1136.55	60
20	400	580.64	1136.55	80
30	400	507.64	1136.55	120

Table 7. Proportion of Ingredients for M3 Mixes after Replacing Cement and Sand

Weight of Materials (Kg)					
% Replacement	Cement	Amorphous Silica	Aggregate	Sand	Waste Ceramic Tiles
0	400	0	1136.55	726.64	0
10	360	40	1136.55	653.64	40
15	340	60	1136.55	617.64	60
20	320	80	1136.55	580.64	80
30	280	120	1136.55	507.64	120

Test Results

Compressive Strength Test Data

Figure 1. Compressive Strength Test Result at 3 Days

Figure 2. Compressive Strength Test Result at 21 Days

Figure 3. Compressive Strength Test Result at 28 Days

Figure 4. Variations of Compressive Strength Test Result at 28 Days

Flexural Strength Test

Figure 5. Variations of Flexural Strength Test Result at 28 Days

Split Tensile Strength Test

Figure 6. Variations of Split Tensile Strength Test Result at 28 Days

Conclusions

Following are the conclusions of the present work:

- By replacing cement with Amorphous Silica in M1 mix compressive strength increases up-to 20% and then decreases with increase in percentage replacement of cement.
- Compressive strength has been found to be highest at 20% replacement of cement by Amorphous Silica in M1 mixes.
- Slump value is decreased by increasing the percentage of Amorphous Silica.
- Compressive strength increases and slump value decreases by increasing the percentage of replacement of sand by Waste Ceramics in M20 mixes.
- Hence, from above results it has been recommended to replace cement about 20% with Amorphous Silica for higher

compressive strength and optimum workability.

- Results indicate that compressive strength increases with the combined use of Waste Ceramics and Amorphous Silica in concrete.
- Slump value is higher in case of M3 concrete mix when compared with M1 and M2 mixes. However, with the increase in percentage of replacement value of slump cone decreases in all the three concrete mixes M1, M2 and M3.
- As partial replacement of cement with ceramic powder waste increase compressive strength, split tensile strength is decreased.
- Up to 20 % replacement of cement with ceramic powder waste gives good compressive strength, split tensile strength and flexural strength in mpa.
- Higher amount of replacement of cement with ceramic powder waste reduces the compressive strength and split tensile strength of concrete because of extra amount of ceramic powder waste is work as inert material and reduces the amount of cement for hydration process.
- In this investigation found optimum percentage of replacement of cement with ceramic powder waste was 20%.

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